

Synthesis and Insecticidal Activity of N⁴-Aryl-N¹-(O,O-dialkyl thiophosphoryl)Piperazines

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Eleven new N⁴-aryl-N¹-(O,O-dialkyl thiophosphoryl) piperazines have been synthesised as possible insecticides by the condensation of N-aryl piperazines with O,O-dialkyl chloro-thiophosphates and tested against *Periplaneta americana*.

VARIOUS disubstituted piperazines have been shown to possess broad spectrum pharmacological properties including antihistaminic¹, anthelmintic^{2,3}, antiemetic⁴, antibacterial⁵, acaricidal⁶ and anti-convulsant⁷ activities. Furthermore, anticonvulsants are known to exhibit acetylcholinesterase inhibition⁸. Organophosphates exhibiting potent antiacetylcholinesterase activity have been used extensively as important insecticides^{9,10}. These observations encouraged us to synthesise the title compounds with the idea that the combined effect of the piperazine nucleus and O,O-dialkyl chloro-thiophosphate might confer much enhanced insecticidal activity on these compounds.

In all eleven N⁴-aryl-N¹-(O,O-dialkyl thiophosphoryl) piperazines(III) have been prepared according to the tentative scheme given below.

N-aryl piperazines(I) obtained according to known procedures¹¹, are listed in Table 1.

Sl. No.	I R	Yield %	b.p. °C/mm	Lit. b.p. °C/mm
1.	2-CH ₃	25	160-1/10	156-7/10
2.	3-CH ₃	25	188-40/10	186.5-87.5/10
3.	4-CH ₃	25	152-3/10	151-2.5/10
4.	4-Cl	40	110/2/2.5	156-7/5
5.	3-CF ₃	35	Oil	m.p. 250-3 as HBr

Thiophosphorylchloride was prepared after the method of Bailar¹².

O,O-Dialkyl chlorothiophosphates(II) were prepared according to the method of Fletcher *et al*¹³ (Table 2).

Sl. No.	II R	Yield %	b.p. °C/mm	Lit. b.p. °C/mm
1.	Ethyl	50	74/7	96-99/25
2.	n-Butyl	53	153/5	95-8/0.7

N⁴-Aryl-N¹-(O,O-dialkyl thiophosphoryl) piperazines(III) :

A solution of N-aryl piperazine (0.02 mole) in benzene (30 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of O,O-dialkylchlorothiophosphate (0.01 mole) in benzene (20 ml) under constant stirring. After complete addition of N-aryl piperazine additional benzene (20 ml) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for further four hours. Then it was cooled and kept overnight. The separated solid, N-aryl piperazine hydrochloride, was filtered off and benzene from the filtrate was removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The crude product thus obtained was distilled in vacuum. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 3.

Sl. No.	III		b.p. °C/mm	Mean K.D. time (hr)	
	R	R ₁		0.5%	0.1%
1.	C ₂ H ₅	H	132-5/1.2	8.5	10.0
2.	C ₂ H ₅	4-Cl	175-80/1	8.5	10.5
3.	C ₂ H ₅	2-OH	170-3/1	7.5	10.5
4.	C ₂ H ₅	3-OH	144-6/1	8.0	10.5
5.	C ₂ H ₅	4-OH	160-3/1.5	8.0	9.5
6.	C ₂ H ₅	3-CF ₃	100-4/1.5	7.0	9.5
7.	n-C ₄ H ₉	H	182-4/1.5	9.5	12.0
8.	n-C ₄ H ₉	4-Cl	160-4/1	9.5	11.0
9.	n-C ₄ H ₉	2-OH	152-4/1	—	—
10.	n-C ₄ H ₉	4-OH	140-3/1.5	10.0	11.5
11.	n-C ₄ H ₉	3-CF ₃	117-20/1.5	10.0	12.5
				4.0	5.5(Control)
				40.0	40.0 Acetone

Nitrogen analysis the compounds is consistent with the respective composition.

Insecticidal Activity :

In the present study topical method of application by micrometer syringe was employed to test the toxicity of the compounds on adult cockroaches¹⁴.

Acetone solutions of the compounds were applied at a dosage of 0.02 ml of 0.5% and 0.1% concentrations. The chemicals were injected between the 4th and 5th abdominal segments on the ventral side and treated insects were kept under observation for 24 hrs. During this period no food was given. For each sample ten replications were performed and insecticidal activity was determined as an average value. Parathion, a standard insecticide was used for control.

All the tested compounds have been found active against cockroaches (Table 3). From the insecticidal data it is observed that compounds nos. 1-6 (R = Ethyl) are more active than the compound nos. 7-11 (R = Butyl).

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